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THE EFFECTS OF JOB STRESS ON EMPLOYEES' JOB PERFORMANCE AND EMPLOYEES' WELL-BEING IN PRIVATE AND PUBLIC SECTORS OF PAKISTAN AS A ROLE OF MEDIATION IN THE WORKPLACE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

This article is directed at determining the effect of job pressure on employees' occupational performance and well-being. This report on observational research focused on some staff in the public or private sectors in Pakistan who are providing training in the business-related fields of organization, planning, and fashion and textiles. Accurate details were obtained from the synopsis in light of the close questions. This research involves 247 Females and 153 males for data collection in private and public sectors such as banks, hospitals, academics, and universities. This study has included a standardized questionnaire using quantitative research methodology. The deductive method is used. The study collected 400 sample responses from staff members using the convenience sampling technique. The PLS-SEM analysis was used for data analysis through Smart PLS 4 and SPSS 24.0 is also used for descriptive statistics and demographic analysis. The path analysis is conducted using hypothesis testing, reliability, validity, discriminant validity using the Fornell and Larcker criterion (FLC), and multi-group analysis. The results show a positive impact on employees' job performance and well-being. Numerous straight-relapse techniques were exploited to test the assumption. The conclusion based on these statistics is that exposure to duty, work effort, and the exclusion of financial incentives or benefits, which serve a great purpose in generating pressure on workers, also diminishes this productivity. Therefore, it is recommended that businesses reduce pressure by reducing accountability, and career-related stress, giving enough liquidation, and directing workers to additionally develop their work execution together with occupation fulfillment.

Keywords: Occupation Stress, Work overload, Time pressure, Mental Health, Employees Performance, Employees wellbeing.

Introduction

In the present day of competencies, work pressure has become an increasingly prevalent issue in work settings, primarily affecting workers at various employment levels.

Stress at work has become a danger to everyone's health, which may have a bearing on their performance. (Ramli, 2019). In a high-pressure work environment and stressful routine, the risks of reduced job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and increased burnout are considerable (Silva et al., 2021). According to Senol-Durak et al. (2021), a rise in stress equals a loss of well-being, particularly when a person lacks adequate coping techniques.

Work pressure is an outcome or response to ecological components. Work pressure has been progressively predominant in the current era, providing moderate representative spirits. The reasons for technological developments, competitive routines, and a range of another general components can all be blamed for job stress. Work pressure is two doubtful advantages that may depend beneficial & detrimental. This may become effective while assisting otherwise inspires individuals toward working harder & better. This will be able to investigate new options, which will lead to better occupation efficiency. While outer forces raise the job force not lead to real results. Each worker experience with work-related stress on a regular schedule, which has an influence on their job performance. A few factors, including inordinate work, responsibility, deficient, compensation an absence of motivators, working environment inspiration, acknowledgment, and so on can to word related pressure few factors, including inordinate work, responsibility, deficient compensation, an absence of motivators, working environment inspiration, acknowledgment, and so on, can add to word-related pressure. Research has shown that work-related stress can have negative health effects, such as causing new types of headaches in female employees (Maki et al.,

2008)." They suggested that higher stress at work caused female employees to get a new type of migraine (Vijayan, 2017). Rita, Atindanbila, and Abepuoring (2013) lead a survey among the clinical guardians of two unique clinics in Ghana to recognize the level of occupational stress and work execution. The audit exhibits that different components of occupation stress affect work satisfaction. 100 clinical guardian have browsed the two centers as an example. To assess the accumulated data from the two centers quantifiable tests like the Connection test and ANOVA. The results show that the level of occupational stress and occupation satisfaction is the same in the two crisis facilities. The result furthermore shows that the level of liability is higher in clinics and there is a delicate negative association between stress and occupation execution among these two centers (Riaz, 2016)

The motivation behind our exploration is to decide factors that cause work stress among the employees in the advanced education area and to investigate whether these variables on job performance, Job Stress, Workplace Environment, Workload, Time Pressure, and Mental Health have a positive or negative impact.

Problem Statement:

Job stress is a common and important issue that affects employees in a variety of businesses and the organization. The modern work environment's expectations and problems, such as excessive workloads, time constraints, and a lack of control, all contribute to rising levels of workplace stress among employees. Chronic stress not only reduces employees' well-being and mental health, but it also has a negative impact on their job performance, job satisfaction, and overall productivity in the workplace. Work overload has been discovered by nervous system specialists as an indication of headache, which has a significant effect on human wellness and effectiveness at labor. Work overload has also been linked to lower job satisfaction and

ongoing concerns about work-life stress (Shah, 2014).

Research Objectives:

1. To measure Job Stress in Employee Performance and Employee Well-being.
2. To measure the Time Pressure on Employee Performance and Employee Well-being.
3. To measure the Mental Health of Employee Performance and Employee Well-being.
4. To measure the mediating role of Workplace Environment between Job Performance and Employee Well-being

Research Questions:

RO1: How does job stress in Employees' Performance and Employees Well-being?

RO2: How does Time Pressure in Employees' Performance and Employees Well-being?

RO3: How does the workload in Worker's Performance and Employees' Fitness?

RO4: What is impact of the Mental Health on Employees Performance and Employees Well-being?

RO4: What are the effects of the mediating role of the Working Environment between Employee well-being and Employee Performance?

Hypotheses:

H1: There is an impact of Job Stress on Employee Performance and Worker's well-being.

H2: There is an impact of Time Pressure on Employee Performance and Employee Well-being.

H3: There is an impact of workload on Employee Performance and Employees Well-Being.

H4: There is an impact of Mental Health on Employees' Performance and Employees' Well-being.

H5: There is an impact on Work Intensity on Employee Performance and Employee well-being.

H6 There is a positive and significant mediating role of Work Environment between Job Performance and Employees' well-being.

Delimitation of the study:

The primary limitation of this examination study is its example size, which is 200 respondents in the event that the example size might build the outcomes can be more summed up in public and private sectors. The delimitation was selecting the people who are currently working in private and public workplaces. The study specifically targets certain aspects of the work environment such as work overload, time pressure, social environment, mental health, work intensity, human environment, and job stress in each sector. The large sample size was also the delimitation.

Significance of Study:

This type of research requires a separate comparison between the public and private sectors. This study uses a separate comparison strategy for analyzing the data. This demonstrates that work stress straightforwardly influences scholastic life as well as an individual's viable life. The study says that many elements contribute to the fulfillment of an individual. In scholarly life if educators feel pressure in their work, is unclear and needs clarification the understudies are not intrigued to get the talk and feel pressure in their review. "if the participants do not experience stress during the final examination, they can freely engage." in the review activities in associations if the employees feel pressure in their work they don't finish their work. People experience pressure at work. This is due to increased strain, reduced job satisfaction, and an increased workload for employees. In this study about strain & employees' job organization and education sectors, the administration attempts to feel their employees peaceful, stress-free, and feel glad for their job. This study aims to compare the effects of job stress on employee performance and well-being in the private and public sectors of Pakistan.

Literature Review

Job Stress and Employees' Performance and Wellbeing:

Talib, (2009) portrays in their review the connection between job performance and job stress. The researcher coordinates their survey with male maritime forces workers in the navy base at Lumet, Malaysia. The study involved a sample of 42 male authorities and non-authorities that explore the impact of work stress on employee job performance, data was collected through a questionnaire. The study indicates that job stress is connected to overall work performance. After effect that review shows that the two's reliability factors had a value greater than 0.80. Most of the male naval force workers are educated with humble levels regarding position completion with an agreeable climate in the working angle.

Job stress was shown to be negatively associated with job performance among employees in the Indian information technology (IT) sector in research conducted by Bhagat, R.S. et al. (2020). To improve job performance, the authors recommend that employers focus on reducing job pressures and enhancing employees' mental Job Stress adversely affects employees' well-being in various studies According to Podsakoff, N. P. (2007) discovered that occupational stress was adversely connected to psychological wellness, including measures of sadness, anxiety, and burnout, in a meta-analysis of 25 studies. Spector and colleagues (2014) discovered that occupational stresses were positively connected to subsequent psychological discomfort across employees in several industries in longitudinal research.

Time Pressure and Employees' Performance and Employees' Well-being:

Time pressure, paradoxically, is the emotional experience of having less time than is needed (or accepted to be expected) to complete a task and be spurred to do as such," composed by (Ordóez et al., 2015) to execute the work in the designated time. It is also described as the time discrepancy between

the available time and the time necessary to complete a task. According to Belias and Koustelios (2014), time pressure was positively associated with work execution among Greek banking personnel. According to the authors, time constraints can raise employees' drive to work efficiently and effectively, which can lead to higher job performance. There is evidence that time constraints might have a detrimental influence on employee well-being (EWB). Time pressure was shown to be positively associated with burnout symptoms among employees in various industries, as revealed in research conducted by Kalimo et al. (2003).

Work Overload and Employees Performance and Employees' Well-being:

Work over-burden is portrayed by Rizzo (1970), as cited by Degu, 2020) as a bungle between the necessities, time limitations, and assets associated with work that exist to meet these prerequisites. It is a well-known fact that the issues of high workload and job stress appear to be increasing day by day, and essentially every worker seems, by all accounts, to be presented with this responsibility issue no matter what their experience or industry to which they have a place (Shah et al., 2012). According to Khattak et al. (2011), employees in Pakistan experience pressure due to workload. Specialized difficulties at work, over-the-top working hours, lacking compensation, and deficient time for family, eventually influence their exhibition. There is a negative relationship between workload and employee performance. Employee performance can be improved by a high workload, this is due to the employee's incapacity to perform the task due to the employee's capacity and ability (Fransiska & Tupti, 2020). There is a negative relationship between workload on employee well-being. Excessive workloads can reduce well-being through both negative emotional and physiological effects Ilies, Schwind, Wagner et al.(2007)

Mental Health

Psychological wellness issues have been

displayed to impact proficient execution. For instance, [Haslam et al. \(2005\)](#) found that individuals experiencing anxiety and depression exhibited worse decision-making and risk-taking behaviors which can be detrimental to organizational performance. Besides, when individuals suffer from ADHD, specific types of work execution endure, for example, coordinated exercises finished under time requirements ([Biederman et al., 2012](#)). Employee mental health has a positive impact on employee performance. The research on the links between mental health and job performance has grown in recent years. We contend that employee mental health is connected to job performance. This viewpoint is consistent with the happy-productive worker theory, which states that mental health is connected to workplace performance ([Luthans F, et.al, 2007](#)), numerous studies have found that poor mental health negatively influences employee well-being, [Kniffin and Colleagues \(2020\)](#).

Work Intensity:

Work intensity is estimated by various developments that catch workplace qualities. Research radiating from low-and center-pay nations on the indicators, pervasiveness, and results of the workforce is restricted to some extent because of the absence of assets and quality information ([Mutambudzi & Vanajan, 2020](#)).

Working Environment:

The environment around an employee while he or her working at the workplace. It incorporates the business' premises as well as different destinations where representatives are participated in business-related exercises or are expected to be available as a state of work. The workplace incorporates geographic spots, yet in addition, the materials utilized by the person while at work. The work environment has previously been investigated by [Warren, \(2006\)](#) with the goal of identifying and characterizing variables that play a critical role in an organization's performance and fostering job satisfaction among employees.

[Ouko \(2011\)](#) the link between job performance, work environment, and employee well-being was investigated in this research of 200 employees in the Indian financial area. The findings revealed about the work environment moderated directed the relationship between work performance & representative prosperity in part. The study discovered that a happy work atmosphere had a favorable influence on employee well-being, which was linked to higher job performance ([Kumar and Sharma, 2019](#)).

Social Environment:

According to research, the workplace social environment is critical for addressing people's needs and encouraging well-being ([Parkes et al. 1994](#)). The assessment of the social environment includes two components relating to social connections at work, one mostly good and one primarily negative. On the plus side, the amount of socialization has increased.

Human Environment:

The human climate incorporates the board and initiative style, correspondence, worker commitment, cooperation, professional stability, and representative preparation. As per [Nel et al., \(2004\)](#), associations should establish a workplace that backings and naturally propels representatives by zeroing in on components like administration, trust, correspondence, and worker improvement to make work fulfillment since individuals are the company's most valuable resource ([Ouko, 2011](#)).

Theoretical Background:

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Dependent variables:

1. Employees Performance
2. Employees' Wellbeing).

Mediating variables:

1. Work Environment,
2. Work Intensity,
3. Human Environment
4. Social Environment

Independent Variable:

1. Job Stress
2. Work overload
3. Time Pressure
4. Mental Health

Research Methodology:

The quantitative analysis side of the research study has been covered using non-probability (convenience sampling). Quantitative analysis is used (Orodho and Kombo, 2002). This sampling strategy is simple to use and explain to others (Basit. A, et al, 2017). The population of the current study was all working employees in Organization. Questionnaires were got filled from the 400 respondents including supervisors, directors, assistant managers, managerial, and others. 200 for each sector was the minimum requirement of my research. We gathered information from Public sectors such as Universities, academics, and hospitals in private sectors in banks such as HBL, MCB, and UBL. The surveys were distributed online and collected in person as well. This deductive method is used for closed finished surveys (Sprenger, 2011). The questionnaire is the tool for information collection from the target population and the questions will be close-ended & structured. The Pool contains a Likert scale which consists of Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Neutral (N), Agree (A), and Strongly Agree (SA) this is useful in primary data.

Questionnaire Research Technique:

This research has a sample size of 400 people. Of which 200 are public sector people and 200 are private sector. The survey is organized into 11 segments. The principal segments comprise of segment data

(orientation, age, capability, work level position, and experience). The questionnaire adopted source is described in the mentioned table.

Results:**Demographic Analysis:**

Table 4.2 shows the demographic analysis of gender, age, qualification, and experience in the public and private sectors of Pakistan.

(Annexure B)**Descriptive statistics:**

After the Data collection From our 200 responses from the public sector and 200 responses from the private sector, the data analysis in which utilized through the SPSS 24 Version. Table 4.2 calculated the descriptive statistics for the variables. It shows that Public sector values are greater than Private sectors

(Annexure C)**Construct Reliability and Validity:**

The readings were all more than the normally utilized model of 0.70. This is the acknowledged dependability esteem range. Assessment of unwavering quality should be possible through a level of consistency that among different factors (Hair, 2010).in composite reliability. As per (Fornell, 1981), assuming the fluctuation removed esteem is bigger than 0.5, merged legitimacy is laid out, and the end is arrived at that the loadings are amazing; by the by, difference separated esteems below 0.5 are viewed as less valuable for the review. The accompanying table shows the outcome.

(Annexure D)**Discriminant validity****Fornell-Larkcer Criterion (FLC)**

The outcome represents the foretell-Larkcer Criterion (FLC) 1981 that measures the Discriminant validity by using the Smart PLS 4. It is standard practice to assess by measuring the model's discriminant validity

using criteria the Fornell-Lacker and Heterotrait-monotrait (Franke & Sarstedt, 2019; Hair et al., 2017). Using the analysis of the averaged variance's squared value for each implicit component of the model. The Fornell-Larcker criteria verify discriminant validity. The findings validated the Fornell-Larcker discriminant validity criteria.

(Annexure E)

Hypothesis Testing :

In PLS-SEM, the crucial step of bootstrapping gives information on the accuracy of factor estimates. This approach derives sub-tests from the first example everywhere, including replacement (Hair, Matthews, Matthews, & Sarstedt, 2017). Bootstrapping provides details about the coefficient estimate's stability. This process involves collecting a massive number of replacement samples from the original sample (Hair Jr. 2016). After running the bootstrap method, SmartPLS provides the t-values for structural model estimates obtained by the approach. The path coefficient findings for all hypotheses are shown in the table below. The connection is significant at the 95% confidence level (= 0.05) if the t-value is greater than 1.96 (p 0.05).

Predictive Relevance:

Table no 4.5.1 shows the predictive strength and significance of all endogenous factors in the structural model. The above table showed that Employees Well-being ($R^2=0.549$, R^2 adjusted =0.535, Q^2 0.311) percent predictability in, on the other hand, JP shows that ($R^2=0.525$; R^2 adjusted =0.510; Q^2 =0.294) percent predictability in the public sector.

In private the above table shows that Employees Well-being ($R^2=0.538$; R^2 adjusted =0.521; Q^2 0.288) percent predictability in, on the other hand, JP shows that ($R^2=0.519$; R^2 adjusted =0.502; Q^2 =0.310) percent predictability has been explained in the

structural model. A model is considered to have excellent predictive relevance, according to Chin (1998), when its Q^2 value is above zero. (Annexure F)

Summary of all Hypotheses Results:

(Annexure G)

Specific Indirect Effect :

In the public table, To find the mediation between JS -> HE -> EWB ($\beta=0.060$; $t=2.12$; $p<0.049$) that shows a positive and significant relationship between them, secondly the mediation between JS -> HE -> JP ($\beta=0.038$; $t=1.264$; $p<0.206$) that shows there is insignificant and no mediating effect between them. JS -> WI -> EWB ($\beta=0.064$; $t=2.121$; $p<0.034$) It shows a positive and significant mediation relationship between them. JS -> WE -> JP ($\beta=0.044$; $t=1.653$; $p<0.098$) shows the insignificant relationship between them. JS -> SE ->EWB ($\beta=0.050$; $t=2.006$; $p<0.045$) that shows a significant relationship between them. JS -> WI -> JP ($\beta=0.088$; $t=2.309$; $p<0.021$) that shows a significant relationship between them. In the above private table To find the mediation between JS -> HE -> EWB ($\beta=0.020$; $t=0.962$; $p<0.336$) that shows the insignificant relationship between them, secondly the mediation between JS -> HE -> JP ($\beta=0.017$; $t=0.864$; $p<0.388$) that shows there is insignificant and no mediating effect between them. JS -> WI -> EWB ($\beta=0.041$; $t=1.504$; $p<0.133$) It shows insignificant and no mediation relationship between them. JS -> WE -> JP ($\beta=0.027$; $t=1.270$; $p<0.204$) it shows insignificant and no mediation relationship between them. JS -> SE -> EWB ($\beta=0.031$; $t=1.483$; $p<0.138$) that shows the insignificant relationship between them. JS -> WI -> JP ($\beta=0.071$; $t=2.008$; $p<0.045$) that shows a significant relationship between them.

(Annexure H)

Multi-group Analysis:

To report the consequences of a multi-bunch examination of way coefficients, specialists commonly give a table or figure that shows the way coefficients for each

gathering, alongside their standard blunders, t-values, and p-values ($p < .05$), they may likewise report how much the way coefficients contrast across gatherings, utilizing a measurement like a chi-square trial for the proper model. Smith et al., 2010; Jones and Brown, 2015). The following tables show the public sector and private sector difference in this research. Table 4.7 shows the path coefficient difference and no significance in the private and public sectors of Pakistan and further MH $\rightarrow$ EWB ($\beta = -0.037$) that shows the small coefficient difference in both types of sector.

(Annexure J)

Mediating Effect:

(Annexure K)

Conclusion:

Pakistan's public and private sectors both, job stress are a serious issue that can have a severe impact on individuals' job performance and well-being. Yet, workplace mediation may play vital apart in reducing the impact of occupational stress on staff. The preceding guidelines can assist employers in creating a working climate that promotes employee well-being, increases job performance, and effectively resolves the effects of job stress. The study's main concern was the effect of workplace stress on workers' productivity. Job stress had a considerable significant influence on employees' Job Performance and Employees Well-being, Human Environment, Social Environment, Work Intensity and Workplace Environment and Mental Health has a significant impact on Employee Well-being, Time Pressure with job performance has also significant impact between them, Work Intensity has a positive and significant impact between Job Performance and Employees' Well-being, Workload has insignificant impact between Job

performance and Employees wellbeing in Private and Public sectors of Pakistan The study's findings indicate that stress related to the workplace is a problem for both male and female employees. The majority of workers across all age groups believe that workplace stress has an impact on their performance.

Policy Implication:

Stress is one of the overall issues of an association. This study will feature the commitment of stress towards managing position execution and the manners in which an association can deal with the stressors. This study will assume a major part in evaluating what perceived organizational support means for work pressure - execution relationship and it will likewise help HR chiefs to see the meaning of hierarchical help in further developing representatives' work execution.

Future Recommendations:

The following recommendation is focused on the study's results and summary in order to reduce job stress in the workplace.

Employers in Pakistan's public and private sectors should make efforts to create a welcoming office atmosphere that promotes cooperation, open communication, and teamwork. This can decrease workplace stress and enhance the well-being and job satisfaction of employees.

Organizations can make more strain-decrease methods, for example, regular counseling lectures, effective planning, health & wellness workshop, and workers' counseling initiatives on a regular basis.

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(Annexure A)

Table 3.1 Data collection Instrumentation

Variable Name	No of Items	Likert Type	References
Job Stress	7	5-Point	Yozgat, U et al.(2013)
Workoverload	7	5-Point	Tesfaye, N. (2022).
Mental Health	6	5-Point	Kieun Lee, J. O. (2022).
Time Pressure	6	5-Point	Tesfaye, N. (2022).
Job Performance	8	5-Point	Joy, A. J., & Kumar, G. G. S. (2018)
Employees Well-being	8	5-Point	Rabindra Kumar Pradhan, L. H. (2019)
Work Environment	5	5-Point	Hardiyono,H.(2017)
Work Intensity	5	5-Point	Boekhorst, J. A.(2015)
Social Environment	3	5-Point	Amakiri, A.J.(2019)
Human Environment	5	5-Point	Ouko, R. (2011).

(Annexure B)

Table 4.1 Demographic Profile (n=400)

Public Sector			Private Sector	
Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	73	36.5	80	40
Female	127	63.5	120	60
Qualification				
Undergraduate	55	27.5	44	22.0
Graduate	88	44.0	95	47.5
Masters	50	25.0	52	26.0
Ph.D.	7	3.5	9	4.5
Age				
20-30	136	68.0	136	68.0
30-40	32	16.0	36	18.0
40-50	26	13.0	21	10.5
50 Above	6	3.0	7	3.5

(Annexure C)

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics							
Public Sector				Private Sector			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Job Stress	400	44.5450	12.26377	150.400	42.6200	12.71274	161.614
Work Overload	400	26.8050	5.16628	26.690	26.3500	5.36764	28.812
Mental Health	400	23.2850	4.74832	22.547	23.0800	4.90242	24.034
Time Pressure	400	22.9700	4.31884	18.652	22.9450	4.54149	20.625
Job Performance	400	31.5700	5.03506	25.352	31.4250	5.27194	27.793
Employee Wellbeing	400	31.5550	4.96490	24.650	31.4850	5.06935	25.698
Work Environment	400	20.0300	3.02736	9.165	20.0350	3.10677	9.652
Work Intensity	400	20.0350	3.25063	10.567	19.9600	3.31107	10.963
Social Environment	400	12.2000	1.90477	3.628	12.1450	1.99345	3.974
Human Environment	400	19.1500	3.44045	11.837	19.0250	3.58169	12.829
Valid N (listwise)	400						

(Annexure D)

Table 4.3 Construct Reliability and Validity

Variable	Public Sector				Private Sector			Average variance extracted (AVE)
	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	
EmployeeWell-being	0.864	0.868	0.894	0.513	0.868	0.870	0.896	0.520
Human Environment	0.842	0.844	0.888	0.613	0.853	0.856	0.894	0.629
Job Performance	0.899	0.899	0.919	0.589	0.902	0.903	0.922	0.596
Job Stress	0.960	0.964	0.964	0.676	0.956	0.966	0.961	0.655
Mental Health	0.895	0.899	0.920	0.658	0.884	0.889	0.912	0.635
Social Environment	0.816	0.854	0.889	0.727	0.826	0.838	0.896	0.741
Time Pressure	0.857	0.862	0.893	0.582	0.842	0.848	0.883	0.523
Work Environment	0.790	0.798	0.856	0.544	0.793	0.799	0.858	0.548
Work Intensity	0.864	0.867	0.902	0.648	0.867	0.870	0.904	0.654
Work Overload	0.871	0.876	0.901	0.568	0.863	0.866	0.895	0.551

(Annexure E)

Table 4.4.1 Fornell Larkcer Criterion(FLC)

Public Sector :	EWB	HE	JP	JS	MH	SE	TP	WE	WI	WO
EmployeeWell-being	0.716									
Human Environment	0.515	0.783								
Job Performance	0.638	0.481	0.767							
Job Stress	0.344	0.342	0.422	0.822						
Mental Health	0.490	0.295	0.405	0.357	0.811					
Social Environment	0.529	0.485	0.399	0.258	0.274	0.853				
Time Pressure	0.574	0.430	0.582	0.503	0.468	0.390	0.763			
Work Environment	0.541	0.565	0.542	0.243	0.406	0.324	0.454	0.737		
Work Intensity	0.555	0.418	0.594	0.281	0.295	0.459	0.474	0.464	0.805	
Work Overload	0.448	0.215	0.417	0.520	0.424	0.323	0.709	0.283	0.347	0.753
Private Sector :										
EmployeeWell-being	0.721									
Human Environment	0.498	0.793								
Job Performance	0.624	0.465	0.772							
Job Stress	0.240	0.209	0.325	0.809						
Mental Health	0.507	0.254	0.439	0.261	0.797					
Social Environment	0.489	0.501	0.346	0.196	0.238	0.861				
Time Pressure	0.582	0.529	0.608	0.430	0.479	0.430	0.723			
Work Environment	0.540	0.559	0.533	0.162	0.363	0.366	0.505	0.740		
Work Intensity	0.540	0.437	0.582	0.227	0.291	0.483	0.515	0.484	0.808	
Work Overload	0.419	0.196	0.402	0.435	0.469	0.306	0.667	0.280	0.336	0.742

(Annexure F)

Table 4.5.1 Predictive Relevance

Public sector	Private sector
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	R-square	R-square adjusted	Q ² predict	R-square	R-square adjusted	Q ² predict
EWB	0.549	0.535	0.311	0.538	0.521	0.288
JP	0.525	0.510	0.294	0.519	0.502	0.310

(Annexure G)

Table 4.6 Hypotheses Results of Private and Public Sector

Public Sector Hypothesis						
Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Significant Yes/No
HE -> EWB	0.174	0.177	0.077	2.261	0.024	Significant
HE -> JP	0.112	0.117	0.078	1.450	0.147	Insignificant
JS -> HE	0.342	0.352	0.068	5.052	0.000	Significant
JS -> SE	0.258	0.265	0.070	3.684	0.000	Significant
JS -> WE	0.243	0.251	0.076	3.185	0.001	Significant
JS -> WI	0.281	0.287	0.078	3.602	0.000	Significant
MH -> EWB	0.213	0.213	0.079	2.690	0.007	Significant
MH -> JP	0.080	0.079	0.082	0.976	0.329	Insignificant
SE -> EWB	0.195	0.188	0.082	2.380	0.017	Significant
TP -> EWB	0.180	0.178	0.082	2.199	0.028	Significant
TP -> JP	0.249	0.246	0.106	2.343	0.019	Significant
WE -> JP	0.180	0.184	0.089	2.022	0.043	Significant
WI -> EWB	0.227	0.233	0.078	2.897	0.004	Significant
WI -> JP	0.314	0.313	0.081	3.877	0.000	Significant
WO -> EWB	0.051	0.051	0.066	0.762	0.446	Insignificant
WO -> JP	0.023	0.025	0.101	0.224	0.823	Insignificant
JS -> EWB	0.572	0.591	0.037	1.539	0.000	Significant
JS -> JP	0.431	0.442	0.063	0.063	0.000	Significant

Private Sector Hypothesis						
Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Significant Yes/No
HE -> EWB	0.098	0.103	0.082	1.192	0.233	Insignificant
HE -> JP	0.081	0.092	0.075	1.077	0.281	Insignificant
JS -> HE	0.209	0.221	0.075	2.767	0.006	Significant
JS -> SE	0.196	0.206	0.068	2.867	0.004	Significant
JS -> WE	0.162	0.173	0.075	2.165	0.030	Significant
JS -> WI	0.227	0.237	0.075	3.035	0.002	Significant
MH -> EWB	0.249	0.253	0.087	2.868	0.004	Significant
MH -> JP	0.150	0.151	0.083	1.798	0.072	Insignificant
SE -> EWB	0.159	0.149	0.084	1.886	0.059	Insignificant
TP -> EWB	0.146	0.139	0.086	1.692	0.091	Insignificant
TP -> JP	0.275	0.274	0.094	2.911	0.004	Significant
WE -> JP	0.165	0.163	0.091	1.820	0.069	Insignificant
WI -> EWB	0.181	0.180	0.087	2.080	0.038	Significant
WI -> JP	0.313	0.313	0.088	3.539	0.000	Significant
WO -> EWB	0.028	0.026	0.073	0.387	0.698	Insignificant
WO -> JP	-0.003	0.001	0.093	0.031	0.975	Insignificant
JS -> EWB	0.248	0.271	0.069	3.606	0.000	Significant
JS -> JP	0.336	0.351	0.066	5.112	0.000	Significant

(Annexure H)

Table 4.6.1 Specific Indirect Effect

Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Decision
Public Sector:						
JS -> HE -> EWB	0.060	0.062	0.030	2.120	0.049	Significant
JS -> HE -> JP	0.038	0.042	0.030	1.264	0.206	Insignificant
JS -> WI -> EWB	0.064	0.067	0.030	2.121	0.034	Significant
JS -> WE -> JP	0.044	0.046	0.027	1.653	0.098	Insignificant
JS -> SE -> EWB	0.050	0.049	0.025	2.006	0.045	Significant
JS -> WI -> JP	0.088	0.091	0.038	2.309	0.021	Significant
Private Sector :						
JS -> HE -> EWB	0.020	0.023	0.021	0.962	0.336	Insignificant
JS -> HE -> JP	0.017	0.021	0.020	0.864	0.388	Insignificant
JS -> WI -> EWB	0.041	0.044	0.027	1.504	0.133	Insignificant
JS -> WE -> JP	0.027	0.028	0.021	1.270	0.204	Insignificant
JS -> SE -> EWB	0.031	0.031	0.021	1.483	0.138	Insignificant
JS -> WI -> JP	0.071	0.076	0.035	2.008	0.045	Significant

(Annexure I)

Figure :2PLS Bootstrapping Illustration Public Sector
(Annexure I)

Figure: 3PLS Bootstrapping Illustration Private Sector

(Annexure J)

Table 4.7 Multigroup Analysis

Path	Difference Group1-Group 2	2-tailed (Group_1 vs Group_2) p value
HE -> EWB	0.076	0.891
HE -> JP	0.031	0.774
JS -> HE	0.133	0.188
JS -> SE	0.062	0.543
JS -> WE	0.081	0.396
JS -> WI	0.054	0.611
MH -> EWB	-0.037	0.522
MH -> JP	-0.070	0.459
SE -> EWB	0.037	0.677
TP -> EWB	0.034	0.843

TP -> JP	-0.026	0.995
WE -> JP	0.015	0.753
WI -> EWB	0.046	0.961
WI -> JP	0.001	0.970
WO -> EWB	0.023	0.774
WO -> JP	0.026	0.929
JS -> EWB	0.324	0.286
JS ->JP	0.095	0.274

(Annexure K)

Table 4.11.1 Mediating Effect

Mediating Effect Hypothesis	Difference (Group_1 - Group_2)	2-tailed (Group_1 vs Group_2) p value
JS -> HE -> EWB	0.039	0.739
JS -> HE -> JP	0.022	0.831
JS -> WI -> EWB	0.023	0.762
JS -> WE -> JP	0.017	0.504
JS -> SE -> EWB	0.019	0.495
JS -> WI -> JP	0.017	0.759